

EFFECTS OF CONVENTIONAL DJS AND LOOP TAIL STENT ON LOWER URINARY TRACT SYMPTOMS

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To compare the Effects of the Conventional DJ Stent and the loop-tail stent on Lower Urinary tract Symptoms.

METHODOLOGY: This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Urology Department, Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation, Karachi, from October 2024 to April 2025. Patients were divided into two equal groups into two groups through randomization software. In group A patients; conventional DJ stent was inserted after completion of URS. In group B patients; LT stent was inserted after completion of URS. All patients were followed for 4 weeks after the primary procedure and USSQ score was determined in-terms of urinary and pain symptoms only.

RESULTS: The average age of participants in Group LT was 38.35 ± 10.1 years, whereas Group DJ had a slightly younger average age of 36.43 ± 10.8 years (*p*-value 0.26). There was no incidence of self-migration and stent encrustation. Additionally, when examining the urinary symptom score (USS), Group LT had a mean score of 1.37 ± 1.45 , while Group DJ had a higher mean score of 3.43 ± 2.69 (*p*-value <0.0001).

CONCLUSION: The loop tail (LT) stent is significantly associated with fewer complications, such as urinary and pain symptoms, in comparison to the DJ stent after ureterorenoscopy (URS).

INTRODUCTION

Urolithiasis, or the formation of stones in the urinary tract, is a global health issue that can impact individuals of all ages and is a significant cause of health complications worldwide [1]. The lifetime risk of developing urolithiasis has shown an upward trend over the years. Research indicates that approximately 50% of individuals with a history of urinary stones will experience the formation of a second stone within the subsequent decade [2]. Ureterorenoscopy (URS) has become a prevalent procedure for the extraction of

urinary stones, the assessment of pelvicalyceal structure, and the investigation of upper urinary tract tumors [3,4]. Following this intervention, ureteral stents are frequently used. The primary function of these stents is to ensure the ureter remains open, particularly in cases where edema may occur due to the procedure, to facilitate the passage of residual small stones, and to prevent the development of strictures following any injury to the ureter [5,6].

Ureteral stents are frequently associated with poor tolerability, which can significantly diminish the quality of life for patients. Research has highlighted a variety of symptoms linked to their use, such as incontinence, increased urinary frequency, painful urination, blood in the urine, a feeling of heaviness in the pelvic region, incomplete bladder emptying, and lower back pain [7,8]. Several treatments have been explored to alleviate these stent-related symptoms, with some demonstrating effective results. The discomfort patients experience is largely due to irritation of the bladder caused by the stents. To address this issue, it has been suggested that alterations in the dimensions, design, and materials used for stents might help reduce discomfort. By decreasing the volume of material present in the bladder, it may be possible to lessen these adverse symptoms [9,10]. The concept of reducing material within the bladder was introduced to minimize the irrigative stimulation of the mucosal lining, aiming to develop more comfortable devices for patients. This idea resulted in the creation of loop-tail (LT) stents, which incorporate a traditional proximal 'pigtail' configuration coupled with a distal end crafted from fine prolene. However, there is limited and controversial evidence concerning the true benefits of LT stents [11,12].

METHODOLOGY

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Urology Department, Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation, Karachi, from October 2024 to April 2025. We included patients aged 18 to 50 years, having a stone size <2 cm, who were planned for URS and stent placement. Patients having active urinary tract infections (UTI), diabetic patients or those having chronic kidney disease (CKD) were excluded. A written consent was signed by each patient.

Patients were divided into two equal groups into two groups through randomization software. In group A patients; conventional DJ stent was inserted after completion of URS. In group B patients; LT stent was inserted after completion of URS. All stents were placed using a retrograde approach under cystoscopic guidance following URS. The length of each stent was selected according to the patient's height. In the single loop group, the lower coil of the stent was cut by 3 cm, and a string was tied to this cut end. The string used

was a prolene 7-0 suture, which was manipulated to create a new knot positioned 1 cm from the end of the stent. The distal end of the string, measuring approximately 15 cm, was left protruding from the urethral opening without being secured to the skin.

All patients were followed for 4 weeks after the primary procedure. After 4 weeks, USSQ was filled by the investigator for each patient. The USSQ consists of 37 questions, each scoring 1 point. The maximum score is 37; the higher the score, the worse the urinary symptoms.

Data analysis was carried out using SPSS v25.0. An independent sample t-test was applied to compare quantitative variables between the groups, while a chi-square test was applied to compare qualitative variables, taking a p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS

The average age of participants in Group LT was 38.35 ± 10.1 years, whereas Group DJ had a slightly younger average age of 36.43 ± 10.8 years (p-value 0.26). The size of stones averaged 1.25 ± 0.8 cm in Group LT and 1.11 ± 0.4 cm in Group DJ, with a p-value of 0.18. In terms of the number of stones present, 58 participants in Group LT had single stones (78.4%) while in Group DJ, 48 participants had single stones (64.9%) (p-value of 0.06). Finally, the gender distribution revealed that 64 individuals in Group LT were male (86.5%) and 10 were female (13.5%), while Group DJ had 59 males (79.7%) and 15 females (20.2%), with a p-value of 0.27 (Table 1).

There was no incidence of self-migration and stent encrustation. Additionally, when examining the urinary symptom score (USS), Group LT had a mean score of 1.37 ± 1.45 , while Group DJ had a higher mean score of 3.43 ± 2.69 . This difference was also statistically significant, with a p-value of less than 0.0001 (Table 2).

On comparison of urinary symptoms between the two groups, significant differences were observed. The Group DJ reported a higher prevalence of intermittent urinary symptoms (25.7%, $p < 0.0001$) and incomplete emptying (31.1%, $p < 0.0001$) compared to Group LT, which had no occurrences. Additionally, Group DJ experienced significantly more frequency of spasms (23.0%, $p < 0.0001$), urgency (56.8%, $p = 0.048$), haematuria (64.9%, $p < 0.0001$), and urge incontinence (47.3%, $p < 0.0001$). The

impact on quality of life was also significant in Group DJ, with 31.1% reporting an adverse effect ($p < 0.0001$). Regarding pain symptoms, significant findings included a higher incidence of pain in the loin/flank region in Group DJ (12.2%, $p = 0.002$) and a notable absence of pain in the kidney area during voiding for Group DJ (0.0%, $p = 0.001$) compared to

Group LT, which had 13.5%. Furthermore, Group LT reported being affected by physical activities (13.5%, $p = 0.001$), while Group DJ did not report any such occurrences. Lastly, pain while voiding was also significantly more common in Group DJ (31.1%, $p = 0.01$) (Table 3).

Table 1: Comparison of Baseline Characteristics Between Group

Baseline Characteristics	Group LT (N=74)	Group DJ (N=74)	P-Value
Age (Kg)	38.35±10.1	36.43±10.8	0.26
Height (cm)	166.65±7.1	164.09±7.7	0.10
Size of Stone (cm)	1.25±0.8	1.11±0.4	0.18
Number of Stones (Single/Multiple)	58 (78.4%) / 16 (21.6%)	48 (64.9%) / 26 (35.1%)	0.06
Gender (Male/Female)	64 (86.5%) / 10 (13.5%)	59 (79.7%) / 15 (20.2%)	0.27

Table 2: Comparison of Study Outcomes Between Group

Outcomes	Group LT (N=74)	Group DJ (N=74)	P-Value
Self-migration (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	N/A
Stent Encrustation (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	N/A
USS	1.37±1.45	3.43±2.69	<0.0001

Table 3: Comparison of Urinary and Pain Symptoms Between the Groups

Urinary Symptoms (%)	Group LT (N=74)	Group DJ (N=74)	P-Value
Weak stream	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	N/A
Intermittent	0 (0.0%)	19 (25.7%)	<0.0001
Incomplete empty	0 (0.0%)	23 (31.1%)	<0.0001
Straining to start	10 (13.5%)	9 (12.2%)	0.80
Frequency of spasm	0 (0.0%)	17 (23.0%)	<0.0001
Urgency	30 (40.5%)	42 (56.8%)	0.048
Nocturia	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	N/A
Dysuria	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	N/A
Haematuria	0 (0.0%)	48 (64.9%)	<0.0001
Urge Incontinence	9 (12.2%)	35 (47.3%)	<0.0001
Impact on quality of life	0 (0.0%)	23 (31.1%)	<0.0001
Pain Symptoms (%)			
Loin/flank region	0 (0.0%)	9 (12.2%)	0.002
Hypochondrium/lumbar region (anterior side of the kidney) groin	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	N/A
Bladder region	10 (13.5%)	6 (8.1%)	0.28
External genitalia	6 (8.1%)	7 (9.5%)	0.77
Affected by physical activities	10 (13.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0.001

Pain voiding	10 (13.5%)	23 (31.1%)	0.01
Pain in kidney area at voiding	10 (13.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0.001

DISCUSSION:

Ureteral stents are commonly utilized following ureteroscopy procedures, even when the surgeries are considered straightforward. Despite this widespread use, there is still a lack of comprehensive data regarding the best type of stent and the ideal duration of their use. Over the past decade, advancements in the design and development of ureteral stents have led to a variety of options now available on the market. These stents differ in materials, lengths, the inclusion or exclusion of side holes, and whether they feature a non-permeating X-ray marker at the tip [13]. Nevertheless, one significant issue remains: the negative impact on the quality of life for patients post-stent insertion, primarily due to symptoms linked to the stents, such as difficulty in fully emptying the bladder, pain, increased frequency of urination, and blood in the urine [14,16].

Studies have reported that the use of suture stents can also be used as a method to reduce patient discomfort associated with standard stents. Betschart et al. conducted a study on the comparison of suture tail stents with standard stents after URS. The authors reported significantly lower USS score in suture stents group, 7.1 versus 13.7 in the standard group. The authors reported that replacing conventional stents with suture stents significantly reduced the morbidity associated with ureteral stents insertion [9].

In a study by Barnes et al., 68 patients were evaluated 33 with stent strings and 35 without. Of these, 42 completed surveys (62%). There were no significant differences in urinary symptoms, pain, health, or work performance at one day, six days, or six weeks after stent removal. The average pain score was 2.5 for patients with stent strings versus 3.1 without (P=0.45). Five (15%) of the 33 patients with stent strings unintentionally removed their stents within four days; none required replacement. 32 of 33 patients (97%) removed their stents at home without problems, while one male patient sought clinic help due to anxiety. There were no cases of proximal stent migration needing ureteroscopy removal [17].

In the present study, we compared SRS in patients receiving LT stents with suture with conventional DJ

stents after URS. We used the USS score for comparison of SRS. Our main focus was to compare urinary and pain symptoms; however, we did not assess general health, work performance, or sexual matters. We found lower USS score in LT group; 1.37±1.45 versus 3.43±2.69 in DJ stent group. So patients with LT group had lower USS score and hence more comfort in comparison to DJ stent insertion group.

Sharma et al. conducted a study on comparison of outcomes of LT sent with conventional DJ stent, the authors reported significantly lower urinary symptoms score; 18.56±3.86 in LT group in comparison to 20.42±4.2 in DJ group [18]. While a study by Bosio et al. did not find any significant difference in urinary symptoms using LT versus DJ stent, with mean urinary symptom score of 29 (24-34) LT group versus 29 (25-34) in DJ stent group [12].

Lingeman and colleagues conducted a prospective study involving 236 patients who underwent ureteroscopic stone laser (URSL) treatment, focusing on the comparison between pigtail and loop-tail ureteral stents. Utilizing the ureteric stent symptoms questionnaire (USSQ), they observed significant findings related to pain management. On the fourth day following the stent placement, patients with loop-tail stents reported a decrease in pain levels. Additionally, those with loop-tail stents required less pain medication on the first day post-placement compared to their counterparts with pigtail stents [19].

This study demonstrated that when a standardized positioning technique is used, the loop-tail stent results in fewer increases in incomplete emptying and bladder pain immediately following ureteroscopy and laser lithotripsy (URSL). The URSL procedure itself significantly impacts urinary symptoms. Nonetheless, the loop-tail ureteral stent emerges as a promising choice to reduce symptoms commonly associated with ureteral stenting.

CONCLUSION:

The loop tail (LT) stent is significantly associated with fewer complications, such as urinary and pain

symptoms, in comparison to the DJ stent after ureterorenoscopy (URS).

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